

Appendix: Estimating the cooling water consumption for an AI query

Based in our proposed methodology [published in Joule](#), which estimates energy per query in Wh for production-scale LLMs served in H100 nodes, we extended the analysis to estimate water use per query in Microsoft’s existing air-cooled datacenters. Microsoft’s new generation of AI datacenters are zero water evaporating designs that do not evaporate any water for cooling (WUE = 0).

We used the same simulated per-query IT energy distributions for models greater than 200B parameters, accounting for the effect of PUE. We then converted energy to water using water-use effectiveness (WUE), interpreted as liters per kWh.

Since 1 L/kWh = 1 mL/Wh, the water per query is calculated as:

$$\text{Water per query (mL)} = \text{IT energy per query (Wh)} \times \text{WUE (mL/Wh)}$$

Annual WUE was provided for each datacenter in the Microsoft fleet hosting H100 nodes across the fleet. We evaluated two WUE conditions. In condition A, WUE is sampled directly from the empirical WUE dataset of company datacenter containing H100 nodes, preserving the observed distribution which is concentrated around zero to low WUE values and skewed to very few high-WUE sites. In condition B, we used the mean WUE across all observations. This condition is more conservative than condition A as it is affected more significantly by the higher WUE values in a few legacy datacenters.

For conversational queries, estimated median water use was 0.004 mL/query under sampled WUE (condition A), with an interquartile (IQR) range of 0.0-0.013 mL/query, and 0.034 mL/query under mean WUE (the more conservative condition B) with IQR range of 0.018-0.067 mL/query. This extremely low water uses per query in the 0.0-0.067 mL/query across both cases, around 5 times lower than those reported in literature, is expected as majority of Microsoft's datacenters employ highly water-efficient cooling systems.